

Project-Based Learning in cooperation with Industry: a case study in a textile company

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Abstract

In the 1st year, 1st semester, of the master's in Industrial Engineering and Management at the University of Minho, students develop a project in interaction with companies, integrating knowledge of the semester's curricular units, using the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach. The objective of this paper is to present the project carried out by a team of students at a textile company, aiming to improve the performance of the dyeing and finishing section. The project followed an agile approach, starting with an analysis/diagnosis phase, followed by improvements development and results discussion. Regarding the theoretical background, this paper is based on PBL as an active learning approach and on the Lean Manufacturing paradigm for the technical work developed in the company. Project management encompassed communication, information and time management, and task organization. Various tools were adopted, namely: WhatsApp and Gmail for communication, Microsoft Teams for information management, and ClickUp for time and task organization. Additionally, specific roles were assigned to team members, peer reviews were carried out, and rigorous milestones and deliverables were set. Regarding technical work, the focus was on creating the necessary conditions to allow the effective calculation of the OEE (Overall Equipment Effectiveness) indicator for the section under study, something that did not exist due to the high diversity of products. Subsequently, using Ishikawa diagrams, it was possible to identify/analyse the main reasons for machines stoppages. The intervention work used PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) cycles. The project produced significant outcomes: students gained direct exposure to the business environment and developed competences in project management, communication, and teamwork. Likewise, the company has also benefited from implementing OEE calculation, identifying process improvement opportunities and adopting Lean Manufacturing practices. This case study highlights the advantages of the PBL approach, demonstrating its positive impact on both students' training and the performance of the partner company.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning; Project Management; Overall Equipment Effectiveness; Lean Manufacturing.

1 Introduction

The increasing complexity of industrial processes and the growing demand for efficiency and adaptability in production environments have intensified the need for innovative educational methodologies that bridge the gap between academia and industry. Project-Based Learning (PBL) has emerged as an effective pedagogical approach that fosters experiential learning, equipping students with the technical, managerial, and teamwork competences required in real-world settings. Although PBL has been widely explored in engineering education, its implementation in close collaboration with industry (real production environments), remains underrepresented in the literature. This study contributes to addressing that gap by examining a University-Business Cooperation (UBC) project developed in the textile sector. In this context, this study explores the implementation of a PBL initiative developed in collaboration with a textile company, aiming to address a practical challenge within the organisation's production system.

The primary objective of this project was to integrate students of the master's in Industrial Engineering and Management, at the University of Minho, into an industrial environment where they could apply theoretical

knowledge to a real case study, focusing on both the technical aspects of production management and the overall project execution. A key component of this integration was the development of team management competences, as students were required to collaborate effectively, distribute responsibilities, and make collective decisions to achieve the project objectives. Regarding the project's technical side, the work specifically addressed the challenges related to calculating the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) of the dyeing and finishing section and proposed solutions to enhance data accuracy and operational effectiveness. By analysing Key Performance Indicators (KPI), identifying inefficiencies, and implementing structured improvements, the project sought to deliver tangible benefits to the company while simultaneously enhancing the students' professional and interpersonal competences.

This paper presents the PBL initiative results, detailing the diagnostic analysis, main challenges encountered, and proposed improvements. Furthermore, it discusses the implications of integrating students into industrial problem-solving and evaluates the effectiveness of PBL as a methodology for bridging academic knowledge with industry needs. Particular attention is given to the role of team management in facilitating collaboration, enhancing problem-solving capabilities, and fostering leadership competences among participants.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Project-Based Learning

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is a teaching method focused on students' active engagement through the resolution of complex, real-life problems. This approach encourages exploration of various pathways to arrive at valid solutions, fostering meaningful learning by stimulating critical thinking, collaboration, and independent knowledge acquisition (Moustafa, & Al-Rashaida, 2024). At its core, PBL is defined by its interactive and interdisciplinary aspects. It involves structured projects where students work together to propose solutions to real-world challenges, enhancing teamwork and active engagement, and aligning with both academic and professional objectives (Tijo-López & Mejía-Aguilar, 2024). The University of Minho (UM) has adopted the PBL approach since the academic year 2004/2005, particularly within the Industrial Engineering and Management program, with several studies highlighting its implementation and positive impact over the years (Alves et al., 2020, 2021; Fernandes et al., 2021; Lima et al., 2017, 2018; Sousa et al., 2023).

Additionally, PBL emphasizes a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical application, allowing students to improve their problem-solving and communication abilities through collaborative workshops and activities; these experiences are essential for their future careers. One significant advantage of PBL is its contribution to developing both practical and social competences. When academic hackathons are integrated into PBL, engineering students, for instance, gain competences in social entrepreneurship, fostering innovation and creating social impact by addressing real-world problems (d'Escoffier & Rezende, 2024).

Moreover, PBL also plays a key role in enhancing emotional resilience and coping mechanisms. Through participatory activities, students are able to face emotional challenges within group settings, promoting personal and professional growth. It also cultivates skills such as empathy, adaptability, and conflict resolution (Martínez & Varela, 2024). PBL stands as a transformative educational approach, empowering students with real-world problem-solving abilities and structured project planning. It prepares them for both professional success and positive societal impact, while simultaneously fostering technical, social, and emotional competencies essential for navigating a constantly changing world.

2.2 Lean Manufacturing

Lean Manufacturing is a management and production philosophy aimed at maximizing customer value through the systematic elimination of waste (Muda) and continuous improvement (Kaizen) of production processes. This approach has its roots in the Toyota Production System (TPS), developed by Taiichi Ohno at Toyota in the post-World War II period, and was later consolidated and adapted for other sectors by various scholars and professionals (Ohno, 1988; Shingo, 1989; Liker, 2005). Developed by Taiichi Ohno in response to the limitations of the Fordist model, the TPS identified seven types of waste (Muda): overproduction, waiting, transport, overprocessing, inventory, motion, and defects (Ohno, 1988). Additionally, a later contribution identified an eighth type of waste - the underutilization of human potential - emphasizing the importance of engaging employees' skills and knowledge (Liker, 2005). The TPS also introduced the concepts of Just-In-Time (JIT) and Jidoka (automation with a human touch) to ensure demand-driven production and built-in quality at every stage (Ohno, 1988). The concept of Lean gained global recognition with the work of James Womack, Daniel Jones, and Daniel Roos, who in their book *The Machine That Changed the World*, analysed the TPS and demonstrated how it was significantly more efficient than traditional mass production models (Womack, Jones & Roos, 1990). Subsequently, in 1996, Womack and Jones systematized Lean thinking into five fundamental principles in the book *Lean Thinking: Banish Waste and Create Wealth in Your Corporation* (Womack & Jones, 1996). Those five core principles of Lean are: defining value, mapping the value stream, creating continuous flow, establishing pull-based production, and pursuing perfection through continuous improvement (Kaizen).

Lean Manufacturing is founded on the principle that value is defined solely by the customer, and thus, all activities that do not directly contribute to value creation should be eliminated. Unlike traditional mass production - characterized by waste, namely excess inventory among others, and limited responsiveness - Lean aims to establish a continuous production flow, delivering the right number of products at the right time, in the right quantity (i.e. JIT), and with minimal waste (Ohno, 1988). In fact, Womack, Jones, and Roos (1990), demonstrated that TPS outperformed traditional models in efficiency, quality, and cost. Their research also emphasized the importance of a culture oriented toward continuous improvement and employee engagement.

Although initially developed for the automotive industry, Lean principles have subsequently been adapted across various sectors such as healthcare, services, and logistics, leading to reduced lead times, enhanced flexibility, lower operational costs, and improved product and service quality. However, successful Lean implementation requires a deep cultural and operational shift, emphasizing continuous waste elimination and active employee participation.

3 Project Development

3.1 Project Management

Upon the presentation of the project's problem statement to the team, it became imperative to identify tools capable of planning and monitoring the project to ensure optimal organisation and the attainment of desired outcomes. The team adopted the Project Model Canvas (PM Canvas), a simplified visual tool for collaborative project planning, which revolves around essential questions such as "Why?", "What?", "Who?", "How?", "When?" and "How much?" (Project Model Canvas Background, n.d.). This tool was pivotal in the visual and direct identification of problems and opportunities that underpin the project. PM Canvas facilitated a detailed definition of the project's deliverables and their integration, while also identifying risks and constraints that could potentially hinder the project's success. It provided a clear timeline for each major task. Moreover, PM Canvas addressed human and financial factors crucial for the project's success, including the team, stakeholders, and costs (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PM Canvas

Efficient communication was a cornerstone of the project's success, particularly in the interaction with the company. Weekly face-to-face meetings at the company were critical to ensuring a clear and direct exchange of information, fostering an in-depth understanding of the project's needs and objectives. Supplementary communication channels such as telephone and email maintained a consistent flow of information, even remotely. For day-to-day interactions, tools such as WhatsApp and Microsoft Teams enabled prompt and immediate responses, facilitating the resolution of urgent issues and promoting agile collaboration.

Microsoft Teams was utilised as the primary communication channel and as a central repository for file sharing and documentation, including meeting minutes, progress reports, and other essential project records. The categorisation of documents enabled swift information retrieval, minimised redundancy, and ensured alignment across all project components. Files were periodically updated not only by team members but also by the company supervisor, which contributed to keeping documentation current and accessible to all stakeholders. This structured and collaborative approach to documentation facilitated coordination and promoted a more efficient workflow. In parallel, the ClickUp platform was specifically adopted for task management, priority setting, and monitoring individual and collective progress. One of the key advantages of ClickUp was its availability as a mobile application, which enabled team members to receive real-time notifications and reminders. This feature proved particularly beneficial in alerting users to approaching deadlines, thereby enhancing time management and responsiveness. These tools were employed in a complementary manner, ensuring functional centralisation of information: Microsoft Teams centralised communication and documentation, while ClickUp structured the team's operational and practical work. The use of these platforms not only centralised relevant information but also served as organised repositories for tracking progress and sharing regular updates, ensuring all participants remained informed and synchronised. Communication with academic supervisors, particularly the project advisor, was strategically important. Regular updates via Microsoft Teams provided a clear and structured view of task progression, while telephone and email contacts ensured swift and effective support whenever necessary. This combined approach strengthened connections between stakeholders and ensured transparent and efficient expectation management.

Following the establishment of planning and communication methods, the team moved on to project monitoring. Microsoft Project (MS Project), a software tool focused on project management, was utilised for its capabilities in scheduling, resource allocation, progress monitoring, and generating useful control reports, namely the burndown chart represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Burndown chart

The burndown chart was essential for monitoring the actual progress of the project (number of tasks remaining) in relation to the idealised progress.

3.2 Work at the Company

The company under study operates in the textile sector, specialising in the production of knitted fabrics and products made from both natural and synthetic fibres. The primary objective of this PBL semester was to combine the academic development of students' technical competences with the resolution of a real-world industrial problem, fostering practical collaboration between university and industry (Lima et al., 2017).

During the initial phase, students conducted an in-depth diagnostic assessment of the company's production line, focusing on some KPI. Particular emphasis was placed on the calculation of Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) of the dyeing and finishing section, which assess equipment performance based on three dimensions: availability, performance, and quality. Several challenges were identified that hindered the accurate calculation of OEE. The company relied on manual records, leading to gaps and inconsistencies in information, particularly regarding standard cycle times, downtime and actual production. Unplanned stoppages were not adequately identified or classified, making it difficult to analyse production losses. Additionally, the monitoring system was rudimentary, lacking digital tools to integrate real-time production data. Another challenge was the limited understanding of the OEE concept among employees, which affected engagement and commitment to improvement initiatives.

Based on this diagnosis, the group proposed feasible and context appropriate solutions, aimed at enhancing operational efficiency and establishing a robust foundation for KPI monitoring. One key recommendation was the automation of data collection, specifically cycle times and stoppages, through the integration of simple hardware into machinery. The adoption of cost-effective software was also suggested to centralise and visualise real time data. In this context, Power BI was employed as the primary data visualisation tool. It enabled the creation of interactive and user-friendly dashboards, thereby enhancing the accessibility and interpretation of performance metrics across different organisational levels. Figure 3 illustrates the dashboard developed for OEE monitoring.

Figure 3. Dashboard for OEE monitoring

In general terms, to support systematic performance tracking, KPI reporting mechanisms were designed and implemented. Weekly and monthly report templates were created for OEE monitoring, incorporating visual tools such as trend charts and loss analysis graphs. Realistic performance improvement targets were defined using historical company data and relevant industry benchmarks.

Standardisation and operational training were also central to the proposed interventions. A structured guide was developed to categorise production losses according to the OEE model, and targeted training sessions were delivered to both machine operators and production managers to ensure consistency in data collection and interpretation practices.

In addition, measures were introduced to foster a culture of continuous improvement involving Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycles. Employees were encouraged to contribute to the identification of root causes of inefficiencies, using Ishikawa Diagrams, and to propose process enhancements. Cross functional communication was also promoted, especially among maintenance, production, and quality departments, to support coordinated and effective corrective actions.

4 Discussion of Results

The project successfully demonstrated the effectiveness of Project-Based Learning (PBL) in bridging academic training with real-world industrial challenges. The structured methodologies employed enabled the team to achieve measurable outcomes in both project management and technical implementation in the company while navigating practical constraints.

The Project Model Canvas (PM Canvas) proved instrumental in establishing a clear project framework from the outset, effectively mapping objectives, deliverables, and associated risks (Ferreira et al., 2020). This visual planning tool facilitated team alignment and maintained focus throughout the project. Complementing this approach, the burndown chart (Figure 2) served as a dynamic monitoring mechanism (Vajda, 2009), allowing the team to track the project's progress. These practices were particularly valuable given the tight academic semester timeframe, allowing the team to balance depth of analysis with timely deliverables.

The core technical achievement involved establishing the foundations for Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) calculation in the dyeing and finishing section. The team developed a product categorization system based on standard cycle times (25 categories), significantly improving the accuracy of equipment efficiency analysis. A notable accomplishment was the development of a Power BI dashboard for performance monitoring

(Figure 3). However, designing an interface that accommodated the diverse informational needs of operators, supervisors, and management tiers presented unexpected challenges, revealing organizational differences in data literacy and usage patterns. It is important to note that prior to this project, the company did not have a procedure for calculating OEE, due to its production environment complexity. As such, this initiative aimed to design and implement the fundamental conditions for monitoring OEE, so it is not (yet) possible to compare before and after values of this KPI. Nonetheless, the work laid the groundwork for future performance tracking and continuous improvement initiatives.

Through root cause analysis using Ishikawa diagrams, the team was able to identify predominant sources of unplanned downtime (setups, worker/shift change, and machine breakdowns), while PDCA cycles enabled structured solution analysis (Taufik, 2020). The team standardized manual data collection procedures to minimize inconsistencies and proposed a plan for future automation of the OEE calculation.

Several operational challenges emerged during implementation, including incomplete production data requiring validation, varying digital literacy levels among personnel, and compressed timelines for solution refinement. These were addressed through feedback meetings with company representatives. The experience highlighted both the potential and limitations of applying academic methodologies in industrial settings, particularly regarding data quality and organizational readiness for change.

This PBL initiative not only delivered actionable improvements for the partner company but also provided students with transformative learning in translating classroom knowledge to industrial practice. As highlighted by Lima et al., (2017) and Fernandes et al. (2014), long-term application of project-based methodologies in engineering education fosters the development of transversal competencies such as teamwork, communication, and problem-solving. Although the project was carried out in a team setting, it is possible to identify individual learning outcomes through the students' grades in the curricular units that supported the project (Project Supporting Courses - PSC) and in the project itself, which reflected each student's capacity to apply technical concepts and tools. On the other hand, transversal competences were mainly evaluated at the team level, through presentations, reports, and project follow-ups. The project highlighted how structured academic frameworks can successfully interface with the dynamic requirements of manufacturing environments when supported by responsive project management and technical adaptability, an approach aligned with the findings of (Alves et al., 2023), who emphasize the importance of university-business cooperation and adaptive pedagogy in enhancing student preparedness for real-world challenges.

Despite the project's achievements, certain limitations must be recognised. Firstly, the lack of a procedure for calculating OEE, as well as for collecting the necessary data in a structured way, has prevented specific improvements from being made in this area. Secondly, the solutions developed were highly tailored to the operational context of a single textile company, which limits their external validity. Moreover, the lack of long-term follow-up prevented the evaluation of the sustainability and broader impact of the implemented changes.

5 Conclusion

The objectives defined at the outset of this study were successfully achieved, as the Project-Based Learning (PBL) initiative enabled students to engage with a real-world industrial challenge while delivering meaningful insights to the partner company. The analysis of the production system, particularly the limitations associated with the calculation of Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE), led to a structured diagnostic process that informed the development of feasible improvement strategies. These included proposals for the digitalisation of data collection and the improved categorisation of production losses, both aimed at establishing a more effective performance monitoring framework.

Throughout the project, several key factors contributed to its successful execution. The use of structured project management tools, such as PM Canvas and ClickUp, played a central role in prioritising tasks and ensuring adherence to timelines. The flexibility of the approach adopted allowed strategies to be adapted continuously in response to evolving circumstances, maintaining alignment with both academic requirements and industrial expectations. Furthermore, the active involvement of stakeholders through regular meetings with company representatives helped to align goals and reduce the effects of unexpected delays. The ability to work with partial or evolving information proved to be an essential skill for managing uncertainty in such dynamic environments.

Despite these strengths, the project encountered several challenges. In the early stages, inconsistencies in manually recorded data hindered the establishment of reliable baseline metrics. In addition, coordinating the timelines and expectations of academic and industrial partners presented logistical difficulties. These issues highlighted the importance of strong internal organisation, effective communication, and the ability to plan flexibly. Addressing these aspects may lead to more efficient execution of future collaborative projects.

A significant outcome of the initiative was the development of both technical and transversal competences. Alongside the application of engineering knowledge, students strengthened their skills in areas such as communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and time management. The experience also emphasised the value of team structure, leadership, and accountability, especially when operating under real industrial constraints.

Looking forward, future efforts should focus on implementing the proposed solutions on a wider scale, including the integration of automated data collection systems and the refinement of OEE monitoring methodologies. Further research could examine the long-term impact of these measures on production efficiency and assess their adaptability across similar industrial contexts. In parallel, continued enhancement of the PBL framework, with particular attention to stakeholder interaction, feedback processes, and collaborative decision-making, could improve the effectiveness of academic and industrial partnerships and further strengthen student preparation for complex professional environments.

By documenting the application of PBL in close collaboration with an industrial partner, this study offers a concrete example of how academic learning can be effectively aligned with real-world practice. It contributes to the limited body of literature on University-Business Cooperation (UBC) within PBL contexts, especially in high-variability production environments. Future research could explore the long-term impact of such initiatives and assess their scalability across different industrial sectors.

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